

3D PRINTED CONTINUOUS FIBRE COMPOSITES: VALIDATION OF DESIGN & ANALYSIS METHODS

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ABSTRACT

In the present study a contemporary damage model is used to predict the performance of 3D printed continuous fibre thermoplastic composites. The damage model has been previously validated against several carbon-epoxy material systems [1], however, it will be shown that the model can successfully predict the behaviour of 3D printed thermoplastic composites. Three laminate configurations were examined, $[\pm 45]_{2S}$, $[\pm 55]_{2S}$ and $[\pm 70]_{2S}$, and these configurations introduce varying magnitudes of shear and transverse stresses. The model was capable of predicting the evolution of plasticity and damage that result in a highly non-linear stress-strain behaviour. The excellent correlation gives confidence that advanced numerical models can be used in forward facing simulations to optimise the topology of 3D printed continuous fibre composites to drive the development of this emerging manufacturing capability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Three-dimensional (3D) printing is a disruptive technology that has transformed traditional design methods that have been based on subtractive machining. The majority of research related to 3D printing has focused on plastic or metallic materials. Researchers have exploited the design flexibility of 3D printing to develop advanced structural topologies that can produce unconventional mechanical properties such as negative Poisson ratio or auxetic structures. These structures are designed using Finite Element (FE) analysis and rely on accurately simulating the mechanical response of the bulk material. Recent advances in technology have enabled continuous fibres to be printed and there are commercially available 3D printers that are capable of printing composite materials. Some of these systems use relatively short fibres or whiskers while other, such as the Mark Two by Mark Forged, can print long continuous fibres. The orthotropic nature of continuous fibres may allow exotic material properties to be produced, however, the question remains, *'how can the design flexibility afforded by 3D printed continuous fibre composites be exploited using advanced analysis techniques?'*

Despite the fact that commercial printers have been available for a number of years the amount of experimental data in the public domain is presently lacking. Contemporary composite damage models require a significant library of test data in order to ensure that the model provides a valid representation of the material. Typically, a number of $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ un-notched coupons with varying angles are mechanically tested to failure. These coupons introduce varying ratios of transverse and shear stresses which allow validation of numerical models over a range of loading conditions. The numerical model must be capable of predicting the material response over a range of ply angles. The model can be assessed using three key metrics:

1. Elastic response,
2. Non-linear material response and
3. Ultimate strength

It is vital that any numerical model can meet each of these three metrics in order to be used in forward facing simulations.

2 ENHANCED PLY DAMAGE MODEL

An enhanced damage model has been proposed by Joosten [1] and this model has shown to be capable of simulating the mechanical behaviour of unidirectional thermoset composites. It is proposed that the model may also be suitable for predicting the behaviour of 3D printed carbon-thermoplastic composites and a brief overview of the model is provided below.

2.1 OVERVIEW

The damage model combines the effect of irreversible damage and plasticity due to the presence of matrix micro-cracking and fibre-matrix de-bonding. The model combines a modified form of the non-linear damage model first proposed by Ladevèze and LeDantec [2] with the well-established Hashin criteria [3] to identify the onset of post-critical failure in the material. The numerical framework is sufficiently robust to facilitate a range of initiation criteria, such as the Puck or LARC criteria, however to date the authors have focussed on the Hashin criteria. Once post-critical failure is detected a crack band model [4] is applied in order to relate the strain energy release rate to the elemental failure strain. The introduction of a crack band model minimises the effect of mesh sensitivity once the element begins to soften. A schematic representation of the pure shear behaviour of the current model is shown in Figure 1. The model was implemented in the commercial FE code ABAQUS explicit using a user defined material subroutine (VUMAT).

Figure 1: Shear behavior of the damage model

2.2 EVOLUTION OF SUB-CRITICAL MATRIX DAMAGE AND PLASTICITY

The sub-critical matrix response is the key feature of the damage model and will be described in detail in the following Sections. The sub-critical matrix response describes the material behaviour prior to the onset of critical matrix damage. For full details of the model please refer to Ref [1]. It should be noted that there is no further progression of sub-critical matrix damage or plasticity once the onset of critical matrix damage has been identified. Critical matrix damage is defined as a stress level that results in the matrix damage onset functions are equal to unity (see Ref [1] for details on the model formulation and numerical implementation). The non-linear sub-critical matrix response results in irreversible plastic strains that are induced by the internal damage state within the material. All of the model parameters in the present are physically based and can be measured experimentally. The coupled plasticity model will be described first followed by the corresponding sub-critical damage model.

2.2.1 PLASTICITY FUNCTION

A yield function with an associated flow rule is used to describe the evolution of permanent plastic strain within the matrix due to transverse (22) and shear (12) loading. The yield function, f , is expressed

as:

$$f = \sqrt{\widetilde{\tau}_{12}^2 + a^2 \widetilde{\sigma}_{22}^2} - R(p) - R_0 \quad (1)$$

with the effective stresses given by:

$$\widetilde{\sigma} = \left[\sigma_{11}, \frac{\langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_+}{(1 - d_{22}^{nl})} + \langle \sigma_{22} \rangle_-, \frac{\tau_{12}}{(1 - d_{12}^{nl})} \right]^T \quad (2)$$

where $\langle D \rangle_+$ and $\langle D \rangle_-$ are Macaulay bracket operators:

$$\langle D \rangle_+ = \begin{cases} D & \text{if } D > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } D \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$\langle D \rangle_- = \begin{cases} D & \text{if } D < 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } D \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

The hardening master curve, $R(p)$, is a function of the accumulated plastic strain, p , and a^2 is an interaction parameter that can be determined using cyclic tests on $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ laminates. Calculating the hardening curve from cyclic test data is discussed in Ref [1]. In the absence of experimental data it is reasonable to assume that a^2 is equal to the theoretical value of 0.33. R_0 is an equivalent yield stress that can be determined via experimental tests. A power law function is used to define the hardening of the material, which can be expressed as:

$$R(p) = \beta p^m \quad (4)$$

where β and η are fitting parameters that can be determined via cyclic testing on $[\pm 45]_{ns}$ laminates.

2.2.2. SUB-CRITICAL MATRIX DAMAGE FUNCTIONS

The transverse and shear sub-critical damage functions are associated with conjugate forces Y_{22} and Y_{12} . These conjugate forces are analogous to strain energy release rates that govern damage development as strain energy release rates govern crack propagation. The conjugate force associated with normal loading is given by:

$$Y_{22} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{E_{22}^0}{(1 - \nu_{12}^0 \nu_{21}^0)} \langle \varepsilon_{22} + \nu_{12}^0 \varepsilon_{11} \rangle_+^2 \quad (5)$$

The Macaulay bracket operator is applied to the effective transverse strain and this implies that there is no sub-critical damage development under transverse compressive loading. It is assumed that matrix micro-cracks associated with sub-critical damage development under transverse tensile loading will close when the material is subjected to a transverse compressive load and the virgin transverse stiffness will be fully recovered. The conjugate force associated with in-plane shear loading is given by:

$$Y_{12} = \frac{1}{2} G_{12}^0 \gamma_{12}^2 + b Y_{22} \quad (6)$$

where b is a coupling coefficient that governs degradation of the material due to shear and transverse loading and this parameter that can be determined using cyclic tests on $[\pm\theta]_{ns}$ laminates where $45^\circ \leq \theta < 90^\circ$ is greater than 45° . If the coupling parameter, b , is set to zero there is no damage coupling between the normal and shear damage modes. Two quantities are introduced in order to describe this development

of matrix damage due to shear and transverse loading respectively:

$$\bar{Y}_{12} = \sqrt{Y_{12}} \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{Y}_{22} = \sqrt{Y_{22}} \quad (8)$$

The development of sub-critical damage is associated with matrix micro-cracking and de-bonding between the fibre-matrix interface. A linear damage law is used to represent evolution of damage under transverse loading:

$$d_{22}^{nl} = \frac{\langle \bar{Y}_{22} - Y_{22}^0 \rangle_+}{Y_{22}^c} \quad (9)$$

where Y_{22}^0 represents the transverse damage threshold and is similar to a yield stress (or strain). The constant Y_{22}^c is associated with the rate of damage development. These variables are typically quantified via experimental tests. A Macaulay bracket operator was applied to the numerator and this ensures that there will be no damage development below the threshold value given by Y_{22}^0 . An upper limit is placed on the transverse damage function which is achieved using the following:

$$d_{22}^{nl} = \min(d_{22}^{nl}, d_{22}^{nl(max)}) \quad (10)$$

The transverse damage is limited to the maximum value of $d_{22}^{nl(max)}$ which represents saturation of matrix micro-cracking within the material. The logarithmic function is used to describe the evolution of shear damage. A logarithmic form of damage has shown to be applicable to a range of composite materials [5, 6]. The shear damage function includes a coupling between shear and transverse loading using the coupling coefficient, B, introduced earlier. The shear damage function is expressed as follows:

$$d_{12}^{nl} = \frac{\langle \ln(\bar{Y}_{12}) - \ln(Y_{12}^0) \rangle_+}{Y_{12}^c} \quad \text{if } \bar{Y}_{12} > 0. \quad (11)$$

The shear damage function is limited to the maximum value of $d_{12}^{nl(max)}$ which represents saturation of matrix micro-cracking and fibre-matrix de-bonding within the material. The upper bound is applied using the following expression:

$$d_{12}^{nl} = \min(d_{12}^{nl}, d_{12}^{nl(max)}) \quad (12)$$

3 APPLICATION TO 3D PRINTED COMPOSITES

The damage model was developed for thermoset composites and has not been previously validated against a thermoplastic composite material system. 3D printed continuous fibre composites consist of long continuous fibres encapsulated within a thermoplastic matrix. The present study will use a contemporary damage model, developed for thermoset composites, to predict the behaviour of 3D printed thermoplastic composites. Unlike autoclave cured unidirectional composites, 3D printed continuous fibre composites are manufactured by consolidating filaments that are consecutively laid down (or printed) along a predefined path, an example of this is shown in Figure 2. It is difficult to characterize the mechanical performance of a single filament, therefore, the authors propose to print each ply with a single fibre orientation. It is assumed that the mechanical performance of each 3D printed layer, consisting of a constant fibre orientation, can be treated in a similar manner to a conventional unidirectional ply.

Figure 2: Example filament printing path (blue) for a 0° unidirectional ply

3.1 SPECIMEN DESIGN AND MECHANICAL TESTING

The current test program focussed on tensile testing of $[\pm\theta]_n$ s laminates where $45^\circ \leq \theta \leq 70^\circ$. These laminate combinations result in varying ratios of shear and transverse stresses (τ_{12} , σ_{22}) and allow the capability of the damage model to be assessed against a number of complex stress states. One issue associated with continuous fibre 3D printing is continuity of the fibre strands. At the edges of the samples the filament printing path results in ‘loops’ of carbon fibres. Additionally there is a region of neat nylon at the edges of the samples (see Figure 3). These features may result in non-uniform stresses across the width of the sample and therefore may violate our previous assumption that each 3D printed layer ‘*can be treated in a similar manner to a conventional unidirectional ply.*’ To avoid this potential problem oversized samples were printed and the edges of all tensile coupons removed prior to testing. This allowed for a more uniform stress field across the width of the sample. The footprint of the samples was 24mm (width) X 160mm (length) and the width was reduced to 20mm prior to testing in order to remove the edges of the samples and produce a uniform fibre topology across the width of the samples.

Figure 3: As printed sample geometry highlighting the fibre ‘loops’ at the edges of the sample. The width of the sample was reduced prior to mechanical testing in order to produce a uniform fibre topology across the width of each sample.

When manufacturing coupons using the MarkTwo printer, the first and last layers of any structure cannot contain fibre-reinforcement and must be printed using nylon, a schematic of a generic layup is shown in Figure 4. This is a hardcoded feature of the software package (Eiger) associated with the 3D printer. The supplier recommends an initial layer of nylon to ensure that the print adheres to the print bed to minimise the likelihood of a failed print. There was no attempt to remove these layers and the mechanical stiffness of these layers ($\sim 940\text{MPa}$) is significantly less than the composite layers.

Furthermore these layers are $\sim 100\mu\text{m}$ in thickness and it is expected that these layer of nylon do not contribute significantly to the overall performance of the composite and were therefore the influence of the nylon layers was neglected in in the present study.

Figure 4: Schematic representation of a 3D printed generic laminate composition that can be produced with the MarkTwo printer

Samples were evaluated using both monotonic and cyclic testing. For further details on cyclic composite testing and subsequent data reduction the reader is referred to Ref's [1,7]. The applied engineering stress was determined based on the initial cross-sectional area of the sample and the strain tensor was obtained via DIC over a 15mm X 15mm gauge area. The stress-strain curves for three laminate configurations are shown in Figure 5. The stress and strain tensors were rotated from the global (test frame) coordinate system to the local ply orientation to allow key material parameters to be extracted from the test data. A comprehensive analysis of all samples was performed and the full details will be reported elsewhere.

2.3 MODEL VALIDATION

FE models of the 160 X 20mm coupons were created with a mesh density of 5.0mm. Conventional shell elements (S4R) were used to represent the sample with several integration points through the thickness. The orientation of the plies was dependent on the specific laminate configuration. In the present study three laminate configurations were examined $[\pm 45]_{2s}$, $[\pm 55]_{2s}$ and $[\pm 70]_{2s}$. A comparison of the model predictions and experimental measurements is shown in Figure 5. The material response is highly non-linear and the model is capable of predicting the material behaviour for a range of laminate configurations and gives confidence that the damage model is suitable for simulating the mechanical behaviour of both thermoplastic and thermoset composites.

Figure 5: Response of 3D printed composites for various laminate configurations. Experimental (dashed lines) and numerical model (solid lines). Left to right $[\pm 45]_{2s}$ (blue) , $[\pm 55]_{2s}$ (red) and $[\pm 70]_{2s}$ (green)

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present study has examined the performance of 3D printed continuous fibre composites and provided an initial validation of a contemporary material model. To the authors knowledge this is the

first work that has quantified the behavior of 3D printed continuous fibre composites with an associated predictive model. The material model was developed for thermoset composites, however, the initial validation demonstrates that the approach can be extended to simulate the highly non-linear material response of 3D printed thermoplastic composites. The development of a predictive model represents a necessary step towards virtual design of 3D printed structures. Future work will focus on detailed validation of other laminate configurations to further assess the capabilities of the material model. These studies will include sample configurations that result in a combined stress state that includes transverse compression and shear.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Joosten MW An enhanced ply damage model for failure prediction in unidirectional composite structures, *Composite Structures*, **207**, 2019 pp. 752-763.
- [2] Ladeveze P, LeDantec E. Damage modelling of the elementary ply for laminated composites. *Composites Science and Technology*, **43(3)**, 1992 pp. 257-267.
- [3] Hashin Z. Failure Criteria for Unidirectional Fiber Composites. *Journal of Applied Mechanics*, **47(2)**, 1980, pp. 329-334.
- [4] Bažant ZP, Oh BH. Crack band theory for fracture of concrete. *Matériaux et. Construction*, **16(3)**, 1983, pp.155-177.
- [5] Johnson AF, Pickett AK, Rozycki P. Computational methods for predicting impact damage in composite structures. *Composites Science and Technology*, **61(15)**, 2001, pp. 2183-2192.
- [6] Johnson AF, Thomson RS, David M, Joosten MW. 10 - Design and testing of crashworthy aerospace composite components. In: Irving PE, Soutis C, editors. *Polymer Composites in the Aerospace Industry: Woodhead Publishing*, 2015, pp. 261-93.
- [7] Joosten MW Experimental and numerical investigation of triggered composite energy absorbing structures, PhD Thesis, UNSW, 2011, <http://handle.unsw.edu.au/1959.4/51438>